

Sol-gel derived Zn-doped mesoporous bioactive glasses for biomedical applications

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Bioactive glasses (BG) continue to attract interest for applications in bone tissue engineering because of their bioactive, osteoconductive and osteoinductive properties. Their application possibilities have covered also the area of soft tissue engineering and wound healing (1). The discovery of mesoporous bioactive glasses (MBGs) opened a new direction for developing multifunctional bioactive materials by applying nanotechnology in regenerative medicine (2, 3). The main goal of the present work is the characterisation of SiO₂-CaO (MBG) and SiO₂-CaO-ZnO (MBG_Zn) bioactive glasses produced by the sol-gel route. The main feature of these nanosized SiO₂-based MBGs is the presence of a highly ordered mesoporous channel structure. The size of dispersed, spherical particles was in the range of 130 ± 10 nm. To connect the regenerative properties of MBGs with the beneficial effect of zinc, MBG doped with Zn²⁺ ions were successfully produced by using microemulsion assisted sol-gel method. EDS analyses and ICP_OES confirmed the presence of zinc in amount ~ 9 mol %. The designed material showed sustained released of zinc ions up to 21 days, reaching its maximum values after 14 days (1,12 mg/L). Cell culture tests with ST-2, MEF and MG-63 cell lines confirmed the cytocompatibility of the tested materials. SEM, XRD and FTIR indicated the formation of hydroxyapatite on the surface of MBG nanoparticles upon 3 days of immersion in simulated body fluid (SBF). On the other hand, the *in vitro* mineralization of MBG_Zn was markedly delayed confirming the same trend already reported in literature (4, 5) This fact can be considered an advantage in some applications such as wound dressing. These positive results confirm the suitability of the obtained MBG as candidates for biomedical applications.

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